

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SAFETY VALVES FOR FACILITIES WORKING WITH GASEOUS FLUIDS

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Abstract

The article presents systematized information about safety valves operating with natural gas and LPG as the main component to ensure safe operation.

Keywords: Safety valves; safety valves for natural gas; safety valves for LPG; gas installations operating under pressure; pressure equipment safety devices

1. Introduction

Safety valves are devices that are widely used in systems and installations using natural gas or propane-butane gas (LPG). Their main function is to protect the system and its elements and aggregates in the event of an overpressure in it, thus protecting it from malfunctions, fire or explosion hazards. Overpressure occurs when the system pressure exceeds the maximum allowable working pressure or the pressure for which it was designed. In order to perform its primary function, the relief valve must be designed to withstand extreme provocations and to maintain its operating parameters under any conditions that may place it, and which tend to place it in conditions of refusal.

They are essentially valves that automatically, without the aid of energy other than that of the respective gaseous fluid, release a quantity of the gas used so as to prevent a predetermined safe pressure from being exceeded. These valves are designed to close quickly after being actuated and thus prevent further gas leakage, thus maintaining normal operating conditions of the pressurized system.

Safety valves can open much faster than exhaust valves. The relief valve (figure 1) opens when a certain set pressure is reached, opening slightly at first and then fully opening so that the unwanted pressure is removed from the system as quickly as possible.

Figure 1. Safety valve

Safety valves have only mechanical operating elements. An increase in the pressure in the system above the maximum allowable operating pressure activates the safety valve, which is able to maintain its operation, even in the event of a power failure, as well as in cases where the electronic or pneumatic safety devices fail. The maximum allowable working pressure is the maximum pressure that the weakest component of the system can withstand at a certain temperature and under normal operating conditions.

To ensure a high degree of reliability in performing their main function, it is necessary to evaluate some essential indicators, such as:

- pressure levels;
- the possibilities of easy assembly and disassembly;
- accessibility;
- possibility of remote monitoring;

- ensuring a safe discharge direction of the working fluid in the event of overpressure.

2. Types of valves and basic elements

There are different types of relief valves, incl.:

- valves with a spring mechanism,
- balanced bellows valves
- pilot operated safety valves.

Each of these types has its advantages, according to the specific conditions in different situations.

The most commonly used safety valves for gaseous fluids are spring loaded and are of two main types: adjustable and non-adjustable.

Spring relief valve is also known as direct acting relief valve. This type of valve has a wide range of application in pressure, which is the limits from 0.1 MPa to 140 MPa. The mechanism of this type of valves consists of the following components (figure 2):

Figure 2

The functional purpose of these components is:

- Spring - the force with which the spring is tensioned depends on what pressure of the working gaseous fluid in the system will begin to open the valve. The spring, which is made of carbon steel, acts on the disc and provides the necessary pressure on the sealing ring, thus ensuring that the normal operating pressure is maintained in the facility.
- Disk - the movable working disk is placed on the nozzle and can move up and down to allow or prohibit the passage of the working fluid through the relief valve
- Expansion Chamber - Increases the surface area that the working fluid in the system presses against to open the relief valve, allowing the relief valve to open quickly
- Nozzle ring - by means of this ring the pressure at which the disk reacts can be adjusted and influenced
- Nozzle - it controls the surface of the disk with which the working gaseous fluid interacts before the valve opens.

3. Calculation of the main parameters of safety valves

The balance between the spring force of the relief valve and the inlet pressure of the fluid controls the opening and closing of the valve. The inlet pressure and the disc surface that the fluid interacts with determine the input force required to open the valve. According to Pascal's law, force is equal to the product of pressure and area. Therefore, as the area of the disc that the fluid interacts with increases, so does the pressure force on the disc..

The efficiency of safety valves is determined by their working gas flow rate κ_p . This coefficient represents the ratio between the amount of the working gaseous fluid that passes with a certain pressure for a given period of time through an opening with a diameter equal to that between the valve and the disc (seat). – $Q_{p\phi}$ and an amount of the working fluid that could pass with a certain pressure for a given period of time through an opening with a diameter equal to the diameter of the disk (saddle) – $Q'_{p\phi}$.

$$k_p = \frac{Q_{p\phi}}{Q'_{p\phi}}, \quad [5]$$

Where $0 \leq \kappa_p \leq 1$ and is determined empirically.

It is essential that the relief valves open quickly and fully to ensure maximum discharge of working gas in minimum time. This is achieved by designing the valve disc diameter to be larger than the nozzle diameter. Under this condition, when the inlet pressure level rises sufficiently, the disk will lift. At this point, the surface area of the disk that can be reached by the working medium increases, which will result in an input force level much greater than the spring force, and the valve will fully open.

The full opening pressure of the valve is determined by the pressure of the working fluid $P_{p\phi}$ and the pressure at the start of the valve opening process P_{ome} and it is

$$P_{no} = P_{p\phi} + \frac{P_{ome}}{100} 10$$

The relief valve vents the working gaseous fluid to prevent pressure build-up, thereby increasing the safety of the system. These valves have an adjustable set pressure and once its level reaches the set limit, the valve will open fully to release the excess pressure. This release usually produces a popping sound. When the pressure in the system normalizes and settles below its maximum set limit, the valve will close, but when the valve returns to normal, its behavior is much sharper and faster. This is due to the effect of the spring on the closing link of the valve, since the overpressured fluid has already been evacuated from the system and there is no effort to smoothly guide the valve to its full closure.

When designing these valves, it should be possible to adjust the set pressure within a certain range. Usually, this adjustment is realized by means of a screw mechanism.

When designing a system working with a gaseous fluid, the correct selection of the safety valve is essential, since it is the element that should guarantee the safety of the system in all cases of overpressure. For this purpose, it is necessary to take into account the following parameters:

- Set opening pressure

- Certain closing pressure
- Gas fluid discharge capacity under overpressure
- Operating temperature
- Type of valve and sealing material

Correctly determining the required safety valve and placing it in the correct place in the pressure system will ensure that the conditions for its safety are met. Designers who construct such facilities with increased danger should carefully consider all the features and specific conditions of the installations they are calculating and, after evaluating all the potential risks related to possible damage and accidents as a result of overpressure, place the safety valve at the defined critical location. In order to implement this process, it is necessary to comply with the requirements of the current normative documents, standards and regulations.

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